

Geopolitics, Critical Minerals, and Energy: The Invisible Infrastructure Powering AI ¹

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Wind turbines spin next to Google's data center in Eemshaven, the Netherlands. Although often associated with abstract concepts like "the cloud," "big data," and "machine learning," artificial intelligence relies on vast physical infrastructure. This significantly increases the demand for critical minerals and has become a key factor in the global power struggle between the United States and China. Image: Google.

On June 11, U.S. President Donald Trump [announced an agreement](#) ¹ with China allowing Chinese students to enroll in American universities in exchange for the supply of rare earth minerals. This measure aligns with recent pressure placed on Ukraine, a country [Trump urged to sign a deal](#) ² granting the U.S. preferential access to critical mineral contracts - especially for rare earths.

This initiative, aimed at reducing U.S. mineral dependency on China, was accompanied by an explicit threat: if the agreement were not signed, [the United States would withdraw its support for Ukraine in the war against Russia](#) ³.

But why are these minerals of such strategic interest to the United States?

The answer lies in the central role that rare earths - and other strategic minerals - play in the physical infrastructure of artificial intelligence (AI), in addition to their numerous applications, [including military ones](#)⁴. Although AI is often associated with abstract concepts such as “the cloud,” “big data,” “machine learning,” and “virtualization” - and thus perceived as an immaterial technology operating solely in the digital realm - it relies on a [vast and complex physical structure](#)⁵. Among its most critical components are data centers: [facilities designed](#)⁶ to house thousands of devices responsible for processing and storing enormous volumes of data.

The Backbone of Digital Technologies

Regarded as the backbone of digital technologies, there are approximately [12,000 data centers](#)⁷ currently operating worldwide, [992 of which are classified as hyperscale](#)⁸ - facilities larger than 10,000 square feet (approximately 929 m²). Some of the largest exceed this size by far, such as “[The Citadel Campus](#)”⁹ in Reno, Nevada (USA), which spans around 669,000 m².

The manufacturing of this ecosystem - which includes [servers, networks, processing units, storage and cooling systems, power supplies, sensors, and cabling](#)⁶ - requires a [wide array of minerals and metals](#)⁶, many of which are [extracted from regions of the Global South](#)¹⁰. Among the most essential are gallium, germanium, metallurgical-grade silicon, tantalum, platinum-group metals, copper, rare earths, silver, and gold, [often refined to high purity levels to meet the electronic, optical, and magnetic specifications of these components](#)¹¹.

Server racks at Google's Mayes County data center in Oklahoma. A wide range of minerals and metals is required to build and maintain such infrastructures. Image: Google.

Short Equipment Life Cycle

For instance, the production of advanced electronic devices may require [50 to 350 times the final product's weight in raw materials](#)¹². This demand is compounded by the [short lifespan of such equipment](#)¹³ - often replaced every two to five years due to rapid [technological obsolescence](#)¹¹. Frequent hardware disposal not only poses [environmental and health risks due to toxic substances](#)¹⁴, but also disrupts the reuse of valuable metals, prompting additional mineral extraction and [increasing pressure on ecosystems](#)¹⁰.

The growing demand for critical minerals has intensified [geopolitical tensions](#)¹⁵ in recent years, becoming a key factor in the global power struggle between the United States and China. Currently, [China dominates the extraction and refining](#)¹⁶ of many materials essential to AI - such as antimony, gallium, germanium, and rare earths - while the [United States leads in](#)

manufacturing¹⁷, which requires high specialization, technological expertise, and intellectual property.

China's Stronghold on Critical Mineral Production

Since 2018, both countries have enacted sanctions, embargoes, and export restrictions involving these strategic resources. In 2023, the [U.S. banned the sale of advanced chips to China](#)¹⁸ and restricted the export of semiconductor manufacturing equipment - measures intensified in October and culminating in the [full suspension of AI-related chip exports](#)¹⁹ by November 2024. In response, [China imposed restrictions on its critical mineral exports](#)²⁰, a domain in which it holds substantial dominance.

Shortly after the start of his second term, Donald Trump met with executives from major AI companies to announce legislative reforms and private investments totaling [US\\$500 billion dedicated to AI infrastructure](#)²¹. During the event, one executive unveiled plans to build [twenty new data centers, each measuring around 46,500 m²](#)²². Days later, the little-known Chinese company [DeepSeek launched DeepSeek-R1](#)²³, a chatbot developed to compete with OpenAI's ChatGPT.

Despite [U.S. restrictions on China's access to advanced chips](#)¹⁹, DeepSeek-R1 was developed at low cost with competitive performance, resulting in an estimated [US\\$1 trillion loss in market value for American companies](#)²⁴. These developments reinforce the [strategic significance of AI and critical minerals in contemporary geopolitics](#)⁵.

High Energy Demand of Artificial Intelligence

Another often-overlooked aspect is the high energy consumption associated with AI. Due to its [intrinsic characteristics](#)²⁵ - such as the use of complex neural networks and the movement of vast datasets across thousands of physical components - [AI applications consume significantly more electricity than conventional digital services](#)²⁶ like emails or web searches. A single interaction with ChatGPT can use up to [ten times more energy](#)²⁷ than a Google search. Image and video generation technologies [demand even more](#)²⁶.

Illuminated servers at Google's data center in St. Ghislain, Belgium. Image: Google.

Data Centers Account for 2% of Global Energy Consumption

According to the International Energy Agency ²⁸, data centers, cryptocurrencies, and AI consumed approximately 460 TWh of electricity in 2022 - equivalent to 2% of global consumption. Projections for 2026 range from 620 to 1,050 TWh. In the United States - [the country with the highest number of data centers](#) ⁷ - these facilities already account for around 4% of national electricity consumption ²⁸. This figure is expected to rise to 6% by 2026 and reach 9.1% by 2030 ²⁷.

A Bloomberg investigation revealed ²⁹ that the increasing energy demand from data centers already exceeds supply in several regions, leading to grid overloads, blackout risks, and rising electricity costs - prompting concern among local communities

Big Tech Invests in Renewable Energy

To meet the growing energy demands of their infrastructure, major tech companies have invested heavily in renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power, aligning their strategies with consumer and investor expectations for sustainability. Amazon, for example, reports operating around [500 global projects](#) ³⁰; Google signed more than [115 clean energy agreements](#) ³¹ between 2010 and 2023; and [Microsoft secured one of the largest corporate contracts in the sector](#) ³², estimated at US\$17 billion.

However, these renewable technologies also [depend heavily on critical minerals](#) ³³ due to their lower energy density, shorter lifespan, and recycling challenges. An onshore wind farm may require up to [nine times more minerals](#) ³⁴ than a gas-fired power plant, while offshore projects may need up to [fifteen times more](#) ³⁴.

The same applies to solar panels, whose production [requires a wide array of strategic minerals](#) ³³. To meet the projected 35 GW energy demand of U.S. data centers by 2030, an estimated 50 million solar panels would be required ⁵ - highlighting the growing pressure on mineral extraction ¹⁰.

This scenario demonstrates that [the expansion of artificial intelligence presents challenges far beyond technological innovation](#) ⁵, encompassing environmental, social, economic, and geopolitical dimensions. Understanding these interconnections is crucial for scientists, civil society, policymakers, businesses, and nations seeking to assess the true costs and implications of AI - and to devise strategies and pathways to address these challenges, particularly if its accelerated growth continues.

Transparency Statement

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